

THE PRINCIPLE OF DEMOCRACY AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN THE CRIMINAL CODE OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: In the article, it is noted that this institute is not able to properly fulfill its function of providing representation of the people in its judicial activities, and it is shown that this situation is caused by some gaps and shortcomings in the legislation, in practice, insufficient importance is attached to the selection of people's advisers, work with them, and their training.

Key words. People's power, democracy, judicial system, criminal court, judge, people's councilor,

Judicial bodies have always been important in protecting democratic values, human rights and freedoms, and legal interests in our country. At the same time, the importance of the Institute of People's Counselors as an effective and practical mechanism for citizens' participation in the judiciary is incomparable in the realization of justice, in creating conditions for increasing their social activity and legal culture, in helping to ensure the balance between the requirements of the law and the interests of humanity in the judicial process.

The participation of people's advisers in criminal cases is one of the important means of ensuring effective interaction between the society and the state. Active participation of the public in court proceedings expands the transparency of judicial activities, strengthens citizens' confidence in the judiciary.

In accordance with Article 13 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Uzbekistan, people's advisers exercise all the rights of a judge in the administration of justice. They have equal rights with the presiding judge in deciding all issues arising during the hearing of the case and passing judgment.

Recently, the expansion of the practice of considering cases in mobile court sessions, the intensive introduction of modern ICTs into the work of the courts - openness and transparency in the work of the court, and the issuance of legal, justified and fair court decisions [1].

The participation of people's advisers in criminal courts is an important factor in ensuring the rule of law and social justice, as well as strengthening social relations between individuals, society and the judiciary. That is why experts in the field have emphasized the significant contribution of people's councilors when court judgments and decisions are changed only in rare cases.[2]

According to the opinions expressed by experts about the unique aspects of the institution of people's advisers in our country, the participation of people's

advisers in court serves to find justice and punish the guilty within the law. After all, the people's advisers, as a person not interested in the results of the case, give their opinion about what kind of punishment is more effective for the defendant, and this is taken into account by the court. It is important that people's advisers work without affecting the independence of judges, and this is one of the important factors of ensuring the open and transparent activity of the judiciary.

The main purpose of studying this criminal-procedural institute is to determine the socio-political and procedural-legal goals intended by the legislator in its introduction, to determine the main useful "work coefficient" of the institute of people's advisers, to analyze its tasks and functions and to develop it.

The legal basis of the Institute of People's Counselors is determined by the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter referred to as the Criminal Procedure Code), the Law "On Courts" and the Regulation "On Qualification Panels of Judges".

In particular, in accordance with Articles 13 and 30 of the Civil Code, when a case is heard by a court of first instance, the court consists of a judge and two people's advisers. Judges appointed or elected to this court and people's advisers who have the opportunity to use all the rights of a judge take part in criminal proceedings.

According to the requirements for people's councilors in Article 59 of the Law "On Courts", a citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan who is not younger than thirty-five years old and who is elected for a period of two and a half years by open voting at a meeting of citizens at their place of residence or work can be a people's councilor. A citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan who is performing actual military service, who has turned thirty-five years old on the day of the election, and who has been elected for a period of two and a half years by open voting at meetings of servicemen of military units, can be a people's adviser of a military court.

It should be noted that people's advisers have been active before. But they had almost no place and role and attended the court only for formalities. According to the data, 15,744 people's advisers were working in the relevant qualification panels of judges of criminal courts and military courts until July 2014 [3]. According to estimates in 2016, a total of more than 10,000 people's advisers were elected to courts in criminal cases.[4]

Currently, a completely new system of justice is being created. In the regulation on the qualification boards of judges, special emphasis was placed on people's

advisers, as well as assigning important tasks and responsibilities to the employees of the field. In particular, the organization of the election of people's councilors is approved by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 22, 2014 "On Amendments and Additions to the Regulation on Qualification Boards of Judges" No. O'RQ-368 regulated by the regulation (new version) on qualification boards"[5].

The qualification board of judges supervises the process of conducting the election of people's councilors, considers the applications and complaints received in connection with the issues of conducting the election, and finalizes the election results; compiles a list of elected people's councilors and issues them with relevant certificates, organizes the training of people's councilors. However, there is still a lot of work to be done in order to further ensure the transparency of the activities of judicial bodies, to expand open communication with the population, and especially to strengthen the role of the public in the administration of justice.

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